

Grid impact analysis on wind power plant interconnection in strengthening electricity systems

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ABSTRACT

The Timor system is one of the large systems in the East Nusa Tenggara region. Based on the general plan for electricity supply for 2021-2030, there is a plan to interconnect a 2x11 MW wind power plant. The addition of wind power plants will pose a considerable threat to the system due to the intermittency nature of renewable energy plants. Therefore, a comprehensive grid impact study is needed to convince network managers that adding wind farms will not cause disruptions to the system either locally or in general and is expected to strengthen the electricity system. The power flow simulation results, installing a 2x11 MW wind farm on the Timor system can improve voltage quality and reduce losses on both 70 and 150 kV systems. For transient stability, the frequency value on the Timor system still meets the grid code requirements. In addition, the simulation results of the intermittency impact of the wind power plant output show that the Timor system is still in a stable condition. The stability of the rotor angle of the existing power plant when the transient stability simulation is carried out shows that it is still in a balanced condition.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Power plants in Indonesia are currently dominated by coal steam power plants, where coal is a fossil fuel that is limited in quantity and will one day run out [1], [2]. Coal cannot be used continuously as the primary fuel commodity in power plants in Indonesia because it produces significant carbon emissions and causes air pollution [1], [3], [4]. Therefore, it is necessary to take strategic steps by changing the energy paradigm, gradually reducing the use of fossil energy, reducing subsidies on energy prices, providing national energy reserves, taking responsibility for regional energy needs and prioritizing energy development [4]-[6].

One of the strategies to reduce carbon emissions is using renewable energy on a large scale combined with energy efficiency efforts [4], [7], [8]. Based on the general plan for electricity supply for 2021-2030, in East Nusa Tenggara province, there is a plan for a 2x11 MW wind power Timor (Scattered Quota) in the Timor system, which is planned to operate in 2024. The construction of wind farm Timor 2x11 MW aims to encourage the utilization of renewable energy generation and achieve the target of an energy mix from renewable energy of 23% renewable energy by 2025 [6]. The nature of the wind farm, whose output power depends on the wind speed, causes the output power to be intermittent [9], [10]. In addition, the wind farm can only operate if the wind speed is above the minimum limit (dead band) and below the maximum wind speed (cutoff) [11].

Understanding grid codes is essential given the rising usage of renewable energy sources, especially wind and solar energy [12]-[14]. The ability to overcome flaws is a crucial feature to take into account. Renewable power plants will be turned off instantly when system faults happen without fault ride-through capability assessments [15], [16]. If renewable energy sources are widely used, there may be significant blackouts on a large scale [17], [18]. This study helps address how the system will be impacted by increased levels of renewable energy penetration as well as for future system accuracy improvements. Intermittent generation has a high risk of uncertainty, so if its composition is above 1% of the actual load power of the system, then its presence impacts system stability. One of the stability aspects that must be considered in operating a power system with a large portion of wind power penetration is maintaining the stability of the power system, namely by maintaining the stability of the voltage profile both in transient conditions and in steady state conditions [19]-[21].

With the planned construction of a 2x11 MW wind farm in the Timor system, research is needed to apply renewable energy sources to the system because of their intermittent [22]. This nature causes generators from renewable energy sources to produce power that changes in magnitude depending on the availability of energy sources [12], [10] to know the condition of the Grid Impact of the Timor 70 kV electricity system after installing the wind farm [23]. The conditions observed in this research are the Power Flow Study on the network system before. After the wind farm is established, the observed power is in the form of active power and reactive power. The voltage profile is also observed at each bus so that there is no overvoltage or undervoltage after the wind farm is installed losses or losses are observed after the installation of the wind farm, whether the presence of losses can decrease or not, transient stability includes voltage and frequency stability [24]-[26] in the existing plant observed before and after the installation of the wind farm whether it is still in a stable condition or not. In this study, Timor system modelling, transient analysis, and load flow will be carried out with needs before and after the interconnection of a 2 x 11 MW wind farm.

2. METHOD

This research applies quantitative analysis methods. The data used in this study was obtained from the 70 kV Timor electricity system in the form of numerical data, which was then inputted and used to simulate power flow (load flow) and transient stability (frequency and rotor angle of the plant). A flowchart with thorough explanations of the study design will be presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research procedure

2.1. Transient stability analysis

Transient stability analysis aims to see if synchronization can be achieved after a machine has experienced a disturbance [17], [27]. Disturbances can come from sudden load shedding, plant trips, significant load losses, or other system disturbances [28]. The equal area criterion method is one way that can be used to perform stability projections quickly [29]-[31]. This approach can only be used with one-machine or two-machine systems connected on an infinite bus.

Figure 2 illustrates the general equal area criterion method where the machine operates at the equilibrium point δ_0 . Figure 2 illustrates the mechanical input power $P_{m0} = P_{e0}$ for the condition. The horizontal line P_{m1} shows the rapid increase of input power. When $P_{m1} > P_{e0}$, the rotor acceleration force is positive, and the power angle δ rises. In (1) can be used to calculate the surplus energy stored in the rotor during the first acceleration [29], [32].

$$\int_{\delta_0}^{\delta} (P_m - P_e) d\delta = \text{area } abc = \text{area } A_1 \quad (1)$$

The electrical power increases with the addition of δ , and when $\delta = \delta_1$, the new input power is P_{m1} . The rotor rotates faster than the synchronous speed, even though the acceleration force is zero [18]. As a result, the power angle δ and the electrical power P_e continue to rise. Now that $P_m < P_e$, which causes the motor to decelerate towards synchronous speed until $\delta = \delta_{max}$, in (2) can be used to calculate the excess energy stored in the rotor during deceleration [11], [33].

$$\int_{\delta_1}^{\delta_{max}} (P_m - P_e) d\delta = \text{area } bde = \text{area } A_2 \quad (2)$$

In (3) is known as the equal area criterion [34], which is derived from (1) and (2). The equal area criterion method can provide a holistic view of power system transient stability by considering all the components involved. This helps identify areas vulnerable to disturbances and enables the development of effective strategies to improve system stability.

$$|\text{area } A_1| = |\text{area } A_2| \quad (3)$$

Figure 2. Equal area criteria for sudden load changes

2.2. Swing equation

The equation governs the rotation/movement of the rotor in a synchronous machine [35], [36]. It is based on the basic principles of dynamics [25], where the acceleration torque is the product of the rotor's moment of inertia (J) with its angular acceleration ($d^2 \theta_m / (dt^2)$) [37], [38]. The following is the rotor dynamic differential equation [2]:

$$J \frac{d^2 \theta_m}{dt^2} = T_a = T_m - T_e Nm \quad (4)$$

where:

- J = Moment of inertia / total inertia of the rotor mass (kg.m^2)
- θ_m = Rotor angular displacement with respect to the stationary axis (rad)
- T_a = Net acceleration rotating moment (Nm)
- T_m = Mechanical or shaft (drive) rotating moment provided by the prime mover minus the decelerating rotating Moment caused by rotation losses (Nm)
- T_e = Electrical/electromagnetic rotating Moment (Nm)

When a synchronous generator generates the electromagnetic torque under rotating conditions with synchronous speed (ω_{sm}), $T_m = T_e$, at the time of disturbance, accelerating $T_m > T_e$ or decelerating $T_m < T_e$ will be obtained [39], [35]. Referring to (4), where θ_m is determined concerning a stationary axis, the calculation of the angular position of the rotor concerning the axis of rotation with synchronous speed can be written as the following (4).

$$\theta_m = \omega_{sm}t + \delta_m \tag{5}$$

Where:

- θ_m = Rotor angular displacement with respect to the stationary axis (rad)
- ω_{sm} = Synchronous speed (rad/s)
- δ_m = Rotor angular displacement commonly called rotor angular displacement against the rotating angle/power angle of the rotating shaft at synchronous speed (radian)

In (6) is a power equation because power equals the product of rotational speed and torque (turning moment) [40].

$$J\omega_m \frac{d^2\delta_m}{dt^2} = P_m - P_e \text{ MW} \tag{6}$$

Where:

- P_m is mechanical power input (MW)
- P_e is the electrical power output (MW)
- Stator copper losses are ignored.

$$\frac{H}{\pi f} \cdot \frac{d^2\delta}{dt^2} = P_m - P_e \text{ pu} \tag{7}$$

In (7) is referred to as the swing equation, which in stability studies is the basic equation governing the dynamics (motion) of synchronous machine rotation [41]. These swing equations are used to analyze the dynamic response of synchronous generators to system disturbances. This analysis helps evaluate the system's transient stability and set up protection and control systems to ensure that the generators remain in synchronization and that the power system recovers quickly after a disturbance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Single line diagram of Timor system

As shown in Figure 3 of the single-line diagram below, the Timor system has three voltage systems represented with different colours. A red line represents the 150 kV voltage system. The yellow line represents the 70 kV voltage system, and the brown line is the 20 kV voltage system. The addition of 2 wind farm units with a capacity of 11 MW per unit connected at the location shown in Figure 3. The selection of the wind power plant interconnection area at substation is due to geographical considerations in the middle of the Timor system and good wind potential (global wind atlas).

Figure 3. Single line diagram of Timor system

3.2. Simulation of load flow in the condition before and after interconnection of 2x11 MW wind power plant

The total load of the Timor system has a load value of 160.29 MW on the generation side, while on the feeder side (load P). After the power flow simulation, the total load of the Timor system has a load value of 160.29 MW on the generation side, while on the feeder side (load P), the load value is 157.7 MW. These results show the difference in the value of the load at the point of generation and load P, which is a power loss with a value of 2.59 MW.

Based on the power flow simulation results with the existing system conditions, a comparison of the conditions before and after the wind farm interconnection for parameters such as voltage and losses is obtained, as shown in Tables 1 and 2. These results show the difference in the value of the load at the point of generation and load P, which is a power loss with a value of 2.60 MW. Based on the power flow simulation results with the existing system conditions, a comparison of the conditions before and after the wind farm interconnection for parameters such as voltage and losses are obtained, as shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Comparison of power losses in the condition before and after wind farm interconnection

No	Voltage system (kV)	Before	Losses (MW)	
			After	
			Interconnection at GI Nonohonis	Interconnection at GI Kefamenanu
1	70	5,93	2,42	1,57
2	150	0,30	0,18	0,17

Table 2. Substation (GI) voltage comparison of conditions before and after wind farm interconnection

No	Location	Voltage system (kV)	Before	Losses (MW)	
				After	
			Interconnection at GI Nonohonis	Interconnection at GI Kefamenanu	
1	Bolok GI	70	66,02	69,48	70,13
2	Maulafa GI	70	65,15	69,05	69,77
3	Naibonat GI	70	64,26	69,37	70,24
4	Nonohonis GI	70	58,69	69,32	70,93
5	Kefamenanu GI	70	55,58	67,65	72,63
6	Atambua GI	70	53,13	65,75	70,90
7	Atapupu GI	70	53,04	65,68	70,84
8	Bolok GI	150	143,33	149,33	150,40
9	Panaf GI	150	143,62	149,53	150,58
10	Tenau GI	150	143,19	149,20	150,28
11	Naibonat GI	150	141,89	148,87	150,08
12	New Kupang GI	150	141,74	148,73	149,94
13	Kefamenanu GI	150	124,37	151,63	162,87
14	Malaka GI	150	124,38	151,72	162,98

The simulation results of Table 2 show that the voltage values in the Timor system at 70 kV and 150 kV voltage systems are still within the range of $\pm 10\%$ voltage variation. The lowest voltage value in the 70 kV voltage system is at Atapupu GI of 65.68 kV, while the lowest voltage value in the 150 kV voltage system is at New Kupang GI of 148.73 kV. The highest voltage value in the 150 kV voltage system is at Malaka GI of 162.98 kV.

According to Tables 1 and 2, the interconnection of a 2x11 MW wind farm in the Timor system can improve voltage quality and reduce power losses for both interconnection locations at Nonohonis GI and Kefamenanu GI. The total power losses in the Timor system after the 2x11 MW wind farm interconnection is 2.60 MW, where the power losses in the 70 kV voltage system are 2.42 MW and in the 150 kV voltage system are 0.18 MW. Compared to power losses before the interconnection of 2x11 MW wind farm, power losses have decreased from 6.23 MW to 2.6 MW.

3.3. Transient stability simulation with wind power plant interconnection

Transient stability analysis to determine the voltage frequency response at the Nonohonis substation (GI) and Kefamenanu GI before and after adding wind farms. Transient simulation is carried out within 50 and will display the results through voltage, frequency and active power graphs. The simulation of the loss of 2 wind farm units has the same regulatory treatment as the simulation of the loss of 1 wind farm unit. Based on Figure 4, the scenario of losing 2x11 MW wind farm causes the frequency to drop to 49.698 Hz and the highest frequency after the system responds to the loss of 2x11 MW wind farm is 50.021 Hz. In the rotor angle graph, it can be seen that the Bolok power plant rotor angle response changes from -13.828 degrees to

9.670 degrees because the Bolok power plant compensates for the power loss of 2x11 MW. It can be seen in the graph that the Bolok power plant has the most significant change in rotor angle response.

Figure 4. Timor system frequency when losing 1 unit of 11 MW wind farm with wind farm interconnection

3.4. Simulation of the impact of wind power plant intermittency on the Timor system

In this simulation, the output intermittency of a 2x11 MW wind farm will be simulated with a scenario based on the realization of a decrease in the output of Tolo wind farm with a capacity of 72 MW. This analysis is done to see how the system behaves during periods of intermittency and identify weak points (system strengths). The simulation results are shown in Figure 5.

The graph in Figure 5 is the power output profile of the Tolo wind power plant, with a capacity of 72 MW on August 28, 2021, which has the most significant decrease in power output throughout 2021. The reduction in wind farm power output occurred from 54.6 MW to 8.5 MW or 46.1 MW (64% of total capacity) in 30 minutes. In accordance with this data, the average decrease in wind farm power output per second is 25.61 kW.

Suppose the percentage decrease in power output is proportional to the capacity of the Timor wind power plant of 2x11 MW (22 MW). In that case, the decline in power output is 14.08 MW in 30 minutes, so the average decrease in power output per second is 7.82 kW. In this simulation, the power output of the Timor wind power plant will be decreased for 9 seconds so that the value of the decrease in power output is 70.38 kW (0.07038 MW). In addition, in this simulation, the setting of the wind farm power output decrease starts from the 3rd second.

The intermittency simulation is carried out by reducing the wind farm's power output from 22 MW to 21.9 MW in 9 seconds. From Figure 6, it can be seen that the decrease in power output to 21.9 MW occurred during seconds 3-12. When the wind farm output drops from 22 MW to 17.5, the lowest frequency value in the system is 49.999 Hz, and the highest frequency is 50.00014 Hz. The frequency value of the simulation results is still within the frequency range set in the Grid Code As shown in Figure 7. When there is a decrease in wind farm power output from 22 MW to 21.9 MW, the existing plants in the Timor system can still return to synchronous and stable conditions, and this can be seen from the rotor angle response of all plants in Figure 8.

Figure 5. Power output profile of 72 MW tolo wind farm

Figure 6. Decrease in wind farm output from 22 MW to 17.5 MW

Figure 7. Timor system frequency when a wind farm output decrease from 22 MW to 22.9 MW within 9 seconds

Figure 8. Generator rotor angle when a wind farm output decrease from 22 to 22.9 MW within 9 seconds

4. CONCLUSION

The installation of a 2x11 MW wind farm can improve the voltage quality of almost all substation busbars in the Timor system. When the 2x11 MW wind farm is connected to Nonohonis GI, the percentage of voltage improvement on 70 kV and 150 kV busbars is in the range of 4.17% - 24.11%. Meanwhile, when the 2x11 MW wind farm is connected to Kefamenanu GI, the percentage of voltage improvement is in the range of 4.92%-33.99%. Due to the better voltage quality, the installation of the wind farm also had an impact on reducing losses in the Timor system, where the total value of losses before the interconnection of 2x11 MW wind farm in 2024 was 6.23 MW, with losses in the 70 kV system amounting to 5.93 MW and in the 150 kV system amounting to 0.30 MW.

Based on the simulation results of the transient stability of the 2x11 MW wind farm installation, the system frequency value is still within the frequency range according to the Nusa Tenggara, Maluku, and Papua Power System Network Rules (Grid Code), namely 49.0-51.0 Hz. For the impact of wind farm intermittency, when operating normally, there may be a decrease in the most extreme output of 64% for 30 minutes from the total capacity of the wind farm. Under transient conditions, there is a change in wind farm output from 22 MW to 21.9 MW within 9 seconds. The frequency value under these conditions shows 49.99 Hz, so it is still in accordance with the Nusa Tenggara, Maluku, and Papua Power System Network Rules (Grid Code).

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